

ANALYSIS OF FILAMENT WOUND PRESSURE VESSELS CONSIDERING THE LAMINATE THICKNESS VARIATION THROUGH THE MERIDIONAL DIRECTION

Theo de Jong, Sotiris Koussios and Otto K. Bergsma
Department of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology,
Delft, The Netherlands

Abstract

The common design methodologies for composite pressure vessels usually neglect the influence of the laminate thickness variation along the meridian profile. In addition, the original fibre path orientation is assumed to remain preserved by neglecting the fibre bundle dimensions. This paper attempts to describe the influence of the fibre bundle geometry and thickness build up on the final performance of the composite vessel under consideration. The obtained results indicate that these properties should generally not be neglected, as the strength of the final product may be lower than the assumed one.

Keywords: filament winding, isotenoids, laminate thickness

Introduction

The applications field of composite pressure vessels is increasingly expanding. To ensure their competitiveness with metal vessels, sophisticated design methods become essential [11,14]. These methods aim to provide accurate estimation of the product performance. In addition, several production process optimisation routines are available, mainly focussed on minimising the time needed to filament wind a vessel.

Focussing on the shape determination of composite pressure vessels, an extensive collection of information can be obtained. The newest developments are usually based on FEM analysis of the incorporated laminates including the influence of their thickness variation across the meridian profile of the shell under consideration [5,7]. The best solution in terms of product performance is then obtained by optimisation techniques. In the preliminary design stage however, a relatively fast evaluation and prediction of the shell deformations and load distribution may be desirable. In this paper, we present a simplified 2-D method for estimating the performance of a pressure vessel, based on the membrane theory. The basis assumptions reflect on negligible matrix contribution and bending stiffness. Due to these assumptions, the method can only be considered as a rough approximation for the determination of the forces and deflection across the meridian profile. However, it provides sufficient information regarding the required shape modification of the vessel in order to improve its performance.

With the typical isotenoidal shape (based on the netting theory) as initial geometry [3,6,10], an approximation for the laminate thickness distribution is constructed. The resulting fibre path geometry is then subjected to the force equilibrium equations. While neglecting the bending stiffness of the laminate, two extreme cases are examined: constant tensile fibre load, and constant load bearing contribution of every layer. In the first case we assume that there is no friction between the fibre layers, and in the second we assume that there is sufficient friction or laminae interaction in order to provide the required tensile load gradient along the fibre length.

Basic equilibrium equations

We consider here an elementary piece of a thin-walled shell of revolution, subjected to some internal pressure P . Two main curvature radii can be distinguished, being perpendicular to each other: the meridional radius of curvature R_μ and the parallel one, R_π . The thickness of the shell is denoted by t .

Fig. 1. An elementary surface piece belonging to a thin-walled shell of revolution

The equilibrium of forces immediately leads to [1,2,4,7]:

$$\sigma_a (tR_\pi \Delta\phi) \Delta\theta + \sigma_r (tR_\mu \Delta\theta) \Delta\phi = F_n = P(R_\pi \Delta\phi)(R_\mu \Delta\theta) \quad (1)$$

Hence:

$$\frac{\sigma_a}{R_\mu} + \frac{\sigma_r}{R_\pi} = \frac{P}{t} \quad (2)$$

The general shell geometry and its basic parameters are given below [6,10]:

Fig. 2. A pressure vessel loaded by an axial force A and internal pressure P .

Every axial cross section (ring element with length ds at a radius ρ) contains N fibre bundles; every bundle is subjected to a tensile force f . Consideration of the force equilibrium of the ring element leads to [6] (note that $ds/dl = \cos\alpha$, figure 2):

$$N \frac{f}{R_v} dl = 2\pi\rho ds P \Rightarrow \frac{Nf}{\pi P \rho} = 2R_v \cos\alpha \quad (3)$$

The radii of curvature can be derived as follows [15]:

$$R_\pi = -\frac{\rho\sqrt{1+z'^2}}{z'} \quad R_\mu = -\frac{(1+z'^2)^{3/2}}{z''} \quad \frac{1}{R_v} = \frac{\cos^2\alpha}{R_\mu} + \frac{\sin^2\alpha}{R_\pi} \quad (4)$$

The characteristic angles α and β are given by:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{z'}{\sqrt{1+z'^2}} \quad \sin \alpha = \frac{\rho_0}{\rho} \quad (5)$$

The axial stress must satisfy the following condition:

$$P\pi\rho^2 + A = 2\pi\rho t\sigma_a \cos \beta \quad (6)$$

The assumption that the fibre belonging to the considered surface element is aligned according to the principal stress direction leads to:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \sigma_a = \sigma \cos^2 \alpha \\ \sigma_r = \sigma \sin^2 \alpha \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow \frac{\sigma_r}{\sigma_a} = \tan^2 \alpha \quad (7)$$

We introduce:

$$Y = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \quad Z = \frac{z}{\rho_0} \quad a = \frac{Nf}{\pi P \rho_0^2} \quad k_a = \frac{A}{\pi P \rho_0^2} \quad R_m = \frac{R_\mu}{\rho_0} \quad R_p = \frac{R_\pi}{\rho_0} \quad R_n = \frac{R_\nu}{\rho_0} \quad (8)$$

Substitution of equations (2) and (6) into (7) and expressing $\cos\beta$ in terms of ρ and R_π (equations (4) and (5)) leads, after introduction of the parameters presented in (8), to:

$$\tan^2 \alpha = \frac{2R_m - \left(1 + \frac{k_a}{Y^2}\right)R_p}{\left(1 + \frac{k_a}{Y^2}\right)R_m} \quad (9)$$

In addition, we obtain from equation (3):

$$a = 2YR_n \cos \alpha \quad (10)$$

Integration of (10) leads to the axial force equilibrium of the shell:

$$a \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{Y^2}} \frac{Z'(Y)}{\sqrt{1+Z'^2(Y)}} = a \cos \alpha \cos \beta = Y^2 + k_a \quad (11)$$

Equations (9), (10) and (11) represent actually the same requirement: the fibre should be aligned with the principal stress direction; at the same time, the fibre direction is dictated by the Clairaut equation. However, every presented expression emphasises on different geometrical aspects; equation (9) matches the fibre orientation with the main curvatures, (10) couples the fibre load to the normal curvature, and (11) expresses the general axial force equilibrium. The solution for equation (11) is [3,4,6,10]:

$$Z'(Y) = - \frac{k_a Y + Y^3}{\sqrt{a^2(Y^2 - 1) - (k_a Y + Y^3)^2}} \quad (12)$$

This expression is only valid for the interval $\{Y_{\min}, Y_{\max}\}$ (selected positive real solutions by setting the argument of the denominator equal to zero), where Y_{\min} is slightly bigger than 1, and Y_{\max} denotes the equatorial radius. Despite the existence of a more elegant representation of (12) in elliptical coordinates [6,10], we will preserve the current expressions for simplicity.

Thickness distribution

The fibre bundle under consideration has a width b and a thickness δ . The fibre bundle placement at the pole is generally not exactly tangential to the polar radius but may be further away; we denote this distance by ϵ . In order to achieve a suitable winding pattern, additional turning around at the polar areas of the vessel may be required. This turning around angle is denoted by Ω [rad]. We further assume that the winding pattern is determined by 3 integer number combinations [8,9]: p = pattern constant (the number of segments before the next circuit is adjacently placed to the first one), dk = number of fibre bundle widths fitting in one segment, and nd = total number of fibre bundles assuring perfect coverage (note: d is the number of the desired reinforcement layers). The thickness of the fibre layer is denoted by t . We introduce:

$$B = \frac{b}{\rho_0} \quad \Delta = \frac{\delta}{\rho_0} \quad E = \frac{\epsilon}{\rho_0} \quad T = \frac{t}{\rho_0} \quad (13)$$

According to [8], the locus ν of the fibre bundle centreline is given by the solution of:

$$(Y_{\min} - 1) + \int_{Y_{\min}}^{\nu} S'(Y) dY = \frac{B}{2} + E - \Delta \frac{Z'(\nu)}{\sqrt{1 + Z'^2(\nu)}} \quad (14)$$

On a similar way, the locus ξ of the outer edge of the bundle is given by:

$$(Y_{\min} - 1) + \int_{Y_{\min}}^{\xi} S'(Y) dY = B + E - \Delta \frac{Z'(\xi)}{\sqrt{1 + Z'^2(\xi)}} \quad (15)$$

We introduce:

$$c = \frac{ndB\Delta}{\pi} \quad (16)$$

By completing the required number of circuits, the averaged fibre thickness across the meridian may be described as follows [5,7,12,13]:

$$T_{complete} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{Y^2 - \nu^2}} \quad (17)$$

For $Y = \nu$, the thickness approaches infinity. This property introduces the need to construct another approach the thickness description at the polar area. The corresponding situation is depicted in figure 3:

Fig. 3. Fibre bundle geometry at the pole

The grey surface, multiplied by $nd\Delta$ should be equal to $\pi(\xi^2 - 1)T_{polar}$. This consideration leads to:

$$T_{polar} = nd\Delta \frac{-2\sqrt{\xi^2 - 1} + (\xi^2 - 1)\Omega + 2\xi^2 \text{asc}\xi}{2\pi(\xi^2 - 1)} \quad (18)$$

where “asc” stays for “arc secant”. The coordinate ν^* where $T_{complete} = T_0$, is given by (figure 4):

$$\nu^* = \sqrt{\nu^2 + \left(\frac{2B(\xi^2 - 1)}{-2\sqrt{\xi^2 - 1} + (\xi^2 - 1)\Omega + 2\xi^2 a \sec \xi} \right)^2} \quad (19)$$

The thickness distribution presented here is generally characterised by satisfactory accuracy. However, in order to properly calculate the curvatures related to a particular fibre layer, the thickness distribution should provide continuity up to the second derivative. For this reason, we introduce the following approximation (figure 4):

Fig. 4. The original thickness distribution (black) and its smoothed approximation (red)

The smoothing process can be realised by a fourth degree polynomial:

$$p(Y) = \sum_{i=0}^4 a_i Y^i \quad (20)$$

The coefficients must satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\nu}^{\nu^*} p(Y) dY + p(\nu)(\nu - 1) &= T_{polar} (\nu^* - 1) & p'(\nu) &= 0 \\ p''(\lambda) &= T''_{complete}(\lambda) & p'(\lambda) &= T'_{complete}(\lambda) & p(\lambda) &= T_{complete}(\lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

with $\lambda = \nu^* + (\nu^* - \nu)$. The obtained coefficients are linearly proportional to c and T_{polar} . Every collection of p circuits is denoted by i . By repeating this collection kd times, the required number of fully closed layers will be achieved (d). Hence, we define:

$$\begin{aligned} T(i, Y) &= \frac{i}{nd} \left(p - \frac{1}{kd} \right) p(\nu) & 1 \leq Y \leq \nu \\ T(i, Y) &= \frac{i}{nd} \left(p - \frac{1}{kd} \right) p(Y) & \nu \leq Y \leq \lambda \\ T(i, Y) &= \frac{i}{nd} \left(p - \frac{1}{kd} \right) \frac{c}{\sqrt{Y^2 - \nu^2}} & \lambda \leq Y \leq Y_{max} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The results of equation (22) agree very well with experimental data and guarantee C^2 continuity for the region of interest: $\{\nu, Y_{max}\}$. A similar method is published by Vasiliev [13].

The obtained thickness distribution is perpendicular to the vessel surface, hence, in order to describe the resulting meridian profile $P(i, Y)$, every obtained T -value should be projected on the Z -axis. This consideration leads to the following expression:

$$P(i, Y) = Z(Y) + \frac{T(i, Y)}{\sqrt{1 + Z'^2(Y)}} \quad (23)$$

where $Z'(Y)$ is given by equation (12). Differentiation leads to:

$$P'(i, Y) = Z'(Y) + \frac{T'(i, Y)}{\sqrt{1 + Z'^2(Y)}} - \frac{T(i, Y)Z'(Y)Z''(Y)}{[1 + Z'^2(Y)]^{3/2}} \quad (24)$$

Assuming geodesic fibre placement, the “real” winding angle is given by:

$$\sin \alpha(Y) = \frac{\nu}{Y} \quad (25)$$

Contrary to [5], we assume here that the thickness build up does not influence the winding angle, since these deviations are in general sufficiently small. In contrast, the influence on the second characteristic angle (equation(5)) can not be neglected:

$$\cos \beta(i, Y) = \frac{P'(i, Y)}{\sqrt{1 + P'^2(i, Y)}} \quad (26)$$

Deformation and load distribution

The axial load bearing capacity (equation (11)) of a particular layer is given by:

$$a(i, Y) \cos \alpha(Y) \cos \beta(i, Y) \quad (27)$$

The validity range of (27) is $\{Y_b, Y_{\max}\}$ where Y_b is generally slightly bigger than ν . If the tensile fibre load $a(i, Y)$ and the orientation $\beta(i, Y)$ remain unchanged, there is no possibility to neutralise the load combination $k_a + Y^2$, see figure (5):

Fig. 5. Load bearing capacity of several fibre layers (red) as function of Y ; the indicative layer number increases from the bottom to the top. The black line represents the applied loads on the vessel.

The inability to create equilibrium can also be viewed by calculating the normal curvature of the vessel including fibre stacking:

$$R_n = -\frac{Y^3[1+P'^2(i,Y)]^{3/2}}{\nu^2[P(i,Y)+P^3(i,Y)+Y(Y^2-\nu^2)P''(i,Y)]} \quad (28)$$

The curvature may obtain negative values in the polar area, while the denominator may also become zero. Consideration of equation (10) leads to the conclusion that there is no real tensile fibre force value, able to create axial equilibrium. Equation (9) leads to the observation that an eventual winding angle correction will not have considerable effect. In addition, there is no solution for Y -values near Y_b . In conclusion, both the fibre force and the β -angle will change.

For the calculation of the resulting meridian profile and fibre force distribution, we assume that every original $\cos\beta$ -value is modified by a quantity $\cos\Delta\beta$. This perturbation is the same for every separate layer. Meanwhile, the resulting fibre force a^* will depend on both Y and the indicative layer number i (in other words: $a^* = a^*(Y,T)$). The initial value at the equator for a^*_{eq} is given by:

$$a^*_{eq} = a \sqrt{\frac{Y_{max}^2 - 1}{Y_{max}^2 - \nu^2}} \quad (29)$$

The cumulative axial forces equilibrium can be expressed as follows:

$$-\frac{1}{kd} \sum_{i=1}^{kd} a^*(i,Y) \cos \alpha(Y) [\cos \beta(i,Y) + \cos \Delta\beta(Y)] = k + Y^2 \quad (30)$$

In addition, an individual layer should satisfy:

$$-a^*(i,Y) [\cos \beta(i,Y) + \cos \Delta\beta(Y)] = D(i) [k + Y^2] \quad (31)$$

where $D(i)$ expresses the load-bearing contribution of the layer under consideration. The simultaneous determination of $a^*(i,Y)$, $\Delta\beta(Y)$ and $D(i)$ should satisfy the condition of minimum deformation energy. In this case however, the solution for this problem becomes rather complicated. Some solution methods are presented in [5,7,11,14]. In this paper, the bending stiffness of the laminate is neglected. With this condition in mind, two extreme cases may be distinguished: constant fibre force $a^*(i,Y)$, and constant load distribution $D(i)$.

a) Constant fibre force

We consider here a pressure vessel covered by unimpregnated fibre bundles and assume that there is no friction between the layers. This immediately leads to the conclusion that the fibre force a^* should remain constant and equal to a^*_{eq} . From equation (30), the new state of deformation $\Delta\beta_0(Y)$ can be obtained. Plugging this result into equation (31) leads to the determination of the load bearing contribution of each individual layer, $D_0(i)$.

b) Homogeneous external load distribution through the thickness direction

We assume now that every layer is able to carry the same fraction of the total load applied on the pressure vessel: $D(i) = (k+Y^2)/kd$. The initial guess for the deformation is: $\Delta\beta(Y) = \Delta\beta_0(Y)$; From equation (31) we obtain the fibre force distribution $a^*_1(i,Y)$. The summation of the fibre forces according to the obtained distribution (for a particular coordinate Y) may be slightly greater than the original fibre force a^*_{eq} (usually limited up to 10%). In order to reduce the total fibre load, we substitute $a^*_1(i,Y)$ into (30) and recalculate the deformation $\Delta\beta_1(Y)$. With the obtained state of deformation and equation (31), a new fibre force distribution can be determined $a^*_2(i,Y)$. The corresponding fibre force summation over the participating layers is $a^*_2(Y)$. This iteration may be repeated until the fibre force summation $a^*_N(Y)$ is sufficiently close to the original one, a^*_{eq} . The final shape is indirectly given by $\Delta\beta_N(Y)$ (equation (32)).

The resulting shape

The validity range of the obtained shape modification is $\{Y_b, Y_{\max}\}$. From equation (27) we obtain the differential equation describing the deformed shape:

$$P'_{\#}^*(i, Y) = \frac{\cos \beta_{\#}(i, Y) \cos \Delta \beta_{\#}(i, Y)}{\sqrt{1 - [\cos \beta_{\#}(i, Y) \cos \Delta \beta_{\#}(i, Y)]^2}} \quad (\# = 0, N) \quad (32)$$

Integration of (32) leads to the geometric description of the “new” meridian profile including the thickness build up. The reduced validity interval makes it impossible to draw any conclusion for the shape at the very near region of $Y = 1$.

Example

The example presented here is based on the original vessel and fibre geometry given in [8]. The winding pattern corresponds with: $p = 15$, $kd = 12$, $nd = 179$ and the additional turn around (Ω) is equal to 0.

a) Constant fibre force

In the figure given below, we depict the original geometry of the implemented layers with black lines, and the resulting ones with red lines. It is visible that the original shape is concave at some regions close to the polar opening; unless the external loads on the vessel should correspond with the average of the red lines given in figure 5, there is no possibility to satisfy the condition of axial force equilibrium. The resulting shape (red) is convex over the entire $\{Y_b, Y_{\max}\}$ -interval.

Fig. 6. Original and deformed vessel shape for constant fibre loading

The load bearing capacity through the fibre layers is given below; the distribution is linear over the shell thickness.

Fig. 7. Load bearing contribution among the fibre layers as a function of Y ; the indicative layer number increases from the bottom to the top

b) *Homogeneous external load distribution through the thickness direction*

As described in the previous section, the original shape modification is given by $\Delta\beta_0(Y)$. To reduce the fibre loads, we apply the proposed iteration procedure. The result after 10 iterations is depicted in figures 8 and 9.

Fig. 8. $\cos\Delta\beta_0(Y)$ (black) and $\cos\Delta\beta_N(Y)$ (purple) after 10 iterations

Fig. 9. $a^*_2(Y)$ (black) and $a^*_N(Y)$ (purple) after 10 iterations.

The original deviation of the fibre force summation (6.2 %) is reduced to 1.4 % ($a^*_{eq}=50.1$). The maximum tensile fibre load in the upper layer is reduced from 81 to 73 (dimensionless number). The tensile force in the lower layer remains practically unchanged (37.3). The original design value for a is 50. The resulting meridian profile shows a limited difference with the one presented in figure 6; the deviation is mainly limited to the polar region.

Conclusions and recommendations

The main objective of this paper is the description of the influence of fibre stacking on the mechanical performance of filament wound pressure vessels. Starting with the description of the basic geometry, an approximation for the fibre layer thickness distribution has been created. With the updated fibre geometry, the static behaviour of the vessel has been analysed, under the assumptions of negligible bending stiffness and no matrix contribution. The analysis contains two extreme cases: overall constant tension load in the fibre bundles, and homogeneous load bearing capacity across the layers. It is believed that these assumptions create the framework in which the mechanical behaviour of a real laminate can be placed.

The results typically demonstrate that, when designing pressure vessels, the effect of fibre stacking should generally be taken into account. In particular, the combination of additional fibre path turn-around at the poles and considerable bundle thickness may increase the deviations in the fibre loads when compared to the design values. Both the assumptions of equal fibre loads and equal load bearing capacity per layer lead to the conclusion that the

vessel performance may be reduced considerably. In the presented example, this reduction is 38 and 46 %, respectively.

Since the presented methodology can only be considered as a rough approximation of the vessel performance, a 3-D model has to be created, based on the classical laminate theory. Inclusion of the matrix contribution and selection of a proper strength criterion should lead to more reliable results. However, it is believed that the presented methodology could prove useful in the design stage of a composite pressure vessel. In this case, the improved meridian profile corresponds with the geometry presented in figure 6 (red lines), under the condition that there is no interference between the fibre layers. In general, increased coherence between the fibre layers (through friction or interlaminar shear stresses) will provide bending stiffness to the laminate. In this case, the membrane theory-based approximation is not usable.

References

1. Baker EH, Kovalevsky L, Rish FL. Structural analysis of shells. New York: McGraw Hill Book Company, 1972.
2. Flügge W. Stresses in Shells. Berlin / Heidelberg / New York: Springer Verlag, 1966.
3. Grammol K. Stress analysis of filament wound open-ended composite shells. <http://eml.ou.edu/Grammol/Research/>, University of Oklahoma, 1997.
4. Hofeditz JT. Structural design considerations for fibrous glass pressure vessels. Modern Plastics, April, 1964: 127-145.
5. Jae-Sung Park, Chang-Sun Hong, Chun-Gon Kim, Cheol-Ung Kim. Analysis of filament wound structures considering the change of winding angles through the thickness direction. Composite Structures 2002: 55: 63-71.
6. Jong de Th. A theory of filament wound pressure vessels. Report LR-379. Structures and materials laboratory, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology. Delft, April, 1983.
7. Kabir MZ. Finite element analysis of composite pressure vessels with a load sharing metallic liner. Composite structures 2000: 49: 247-255.
8. Koussios S, Bergsma OK. Winding pattern determination for pressure vessels comprising fibre bundles of finite dimensions. To appear in: Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Composite Materials, San Diego, CA, July 2003.
9. Koussios S. Influence of the fibre bundle bandwidth on the determination of a winding pattern. In: Proceedings of the ESA European conference on Spacecraft Structures, Materials and mechanical Testing. Noordwijk, November, 2000: 375-381.
10. Nieuwenhuizen E. Composite LPG fuel containers for motor vehicles. M.Sc. thesis report. Structures and materials laboratory, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology. Delft, August, 1995.
11. Parnas L, Katirci N. Design of fibre-reinforced composite pressure vessels under various loading conditions. Composite structures, 2002: 58: 83-95.
12. Rijswijk K van, Koussios S, Bergsma OK. Fibre thickness distribution of a filament wound rotational symmetric pressure vessel. In: Proceedings of the third European conference on launcher technology. Strasbourg, December, 2001.
13. Vasiliev VV, Krikanov AA. New generation of filament-wound composite pressure vessels for commercial applications. In: Proceedings of the fourth international conference on composite science and technology, ICCST 4, Durban, South Africa, January, 2003:10-29.
14. Wild PM, Vickers GW. Analysis of filament wound cylindrical shells under combined centrifugal, pressure and axial loading. Composites Part A: Applied science and manufacturing 1997: 28A: 47-55.
15. www.mathworld.wolfram.com